

Does Financial Performance Influence Green Banking Adoption?

Prepared by

Sumiya Shanta

Department of Business Administration

East West University

Supervisors

Dr. Nikhil Chandra Shil

Professor, Department of Business Administration

East West University

Nazmul Hassan

Senior Lecturer

Department of Business Administration

East West University

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between green banking practices and the financial performance of commercial banks in Bangladesh. Using secondary data from five banks covering 2018–2022, the study applies descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and regression modelling. The findings indicate positive and statistically significant relationships between the Green Banking Index and profitability indicators such as Return on Assets (ROA) and Earnings Per Share (EPS). The results suggest that sustainable banking practices may contribute to long-term competitiveness, transparency, and financial resilience.

Chapter 01: Introduction

Green banking refers to transforming the financial sector to prioritize environmental sustainability. It is any form of banking that benefits the environment. Green banking invests in industries and projects that promote sustainability such as renewable energy, energy-efficient infrastructure and sustainable farming. At the same time, green banks avoid financing activities that harm the environment, such as fossil fuel extraction. They adopt paperless processes, digital banking tools, and energy-efficient practices, showing customers and businesses the value of sustainability. This study aims to show the connection between the independent and dependent variables of green banking and its financial performance. It seeks to understand the relationship between financial performance and a bank's commitment to Practice green banking.

Many theories explain the relationship between financial performance and green banking. Researchers in many developed countries have found a relationship where banks with strong financial performance have the necessary resources to invest in sustainable initiatives, leading to competitive advantages and long-term profitability (Barney, 1991). In countries like the U.S. and Germany, they found that those banks that practice the green banking approach have a good relationship with stakeholders. As Bangladesh is a growing country, this research examines whether there is any potential to increase the green banking index for the bank's profitability.

This study employed quantitative analysis. All data were collected from secondary sources, including the Green Banking Policy of Bangladesh Bank, research papers, journals, bank annual reports, and green banking reports from banks and websites. To evaluate the study's quality, we applied various statistical procedures, such as descriptive analysis, correlation analysis, and a regression model, using the SPSS program.

The findings of this study confirm the significant positive influence of ROA and EPS on the Green Banking Index. Profitability is crucial for improving green banking performance, while equity efficiency has a minimal effect on green banking practices. Financial indicators have a moderate level of explanatory power in the green banking index.

Chapter 02: Literature Review

Green Banking has gained significant attention worldwide (Biswas, 2011), focusing on reducing environmental degradation and ensuring a sustainable, habitable planet. The concept encompasses various aspects, from environmentally conscious practices within banks to the ethical allocation of their financial resources (Mishra, 2010).

Green banking is a strategic approach that is designed to ensure that financial practices are in accordance with environmental sustainability. It has expanded to encompass a wide variety of practices, including the funding of eco-friendly initiatives and the reduction of the carbon footprint of banking operations, since its inception in Western nations (Biswas, 2011). In 2003, the Equator Principles were introduced, marking a significant milestone by establishing a framework for the assessment of environmental and social hazards in project financing (Principles, 2006). This transition toward sustainable finance was signaled by the adoption of these principles by major global institutions, such as Citigroup Inc. and HSBC. Measures such as the Green Channel Counter, no-queue banking, enhanced commitment to attaining carbon neutrality, online money transfers, and wind farms have been implemented by SBI.

The process of Green Banking Disclosure (GBD), which involves banks disclosing their sustainability practices, has become a focal point for stakeholders who are interested in transparency and accountability. The correlation between financial performance and GBD has garnered substantial academic interest. Banks with strong financial performance have the potential to leverage their resources to invest in green initiatives, which could result in increased disclosure. However, this relationship continues to be intricate, as it is impacted by market conditions, stakeholder expectations, and regulatory frameworks. This review examines the relationship between financial performance and GBD, particularly in the context of emerging economies like Bangladesh, and incorporates global perspectives and region-specific insights (Bibhu N R, 2017).

The Green Products and Services initiative of ICICI Bank includes event meetings, media, and websites. The study emphasizes the necessity of well-formulated green policy guidelines for the effective implementation of Green Banking. In India, SBI and ICICI play significant roles in expanding green banking opportunities, leading to the growing popularity of Green Banking. In

addition, the utilization of paper currency has decreased as an increasing number of individuals depend on digital payment platforms such as Gpay, Amazon Pay, BHIM, Paytm, PhonePe, and Kotak for bill payments and purchases (Jaggi, 2014).

The adoption of green banking in emerging markets has been slower, but it is currently gaining growth. In 2011, the Bangladesh Bank implemented comprehensive guidelines to promote sustainable practices among local institutions. These initiatives have been crucial in the incorporation of green banking into national economic strategies, despite challenges such as lack of resources and limited awareness (Rahman, 2011).

The concept of environmentally friendly finance is important to distinguish the different steps taken by the banks with regard to the concept of eco-friendly banking, influencing the clients and making it easier for them to understand. Through these concepts and practices, positive effects have been found to reduce employee concerns and make banks sustainable in financial, climate and social (Sahoo, 2016).

The operations of green banking carried out in specific areas and strategies aimed at reducing global carbon emissions. The significance of green banking is not limited to environmental benefits. It improves operational efficiency, decreases expenses, and fosters stakeholder confidence. In addition to reinforcing a bank's market position, practices such as automated banking and energy-efficient technologies also contribute to sustainability (Bahl, 2012). Additionally, the significance of banks in the promotion of responsible consumer behavior through green financial products is underscored (Silvia, 2015).

The implementation of banking practices that prioritize sustainability in financial operations and services aimed at achieving environmental benefits. This approach encourages the adoption of environmentally conscious behavior by clients and partners, thereby reducing the environmental impact of banking activities (Narang, 2015).

The situation appears to be alarming in the context of Bangladesh. The general population has minimal awareness of environmental pollution and fails to recognize the severe consequences of this pollution, which could lead to significant challenges in the coming decades (Islam, 2018). Banking with technology analyzed the technologies employed by the banking industry to promote environmental sustainability (Khedekar, 2014). The research emphasizes the importance of banks

offering both basic and premium internet banking services. Also recommend that banks should organize seminars and conferences to educate the public on using internet banking and addressing associated security concerns. They also propose the concept of “Virtual Banking,” where customers, particularly those far from main branches, can access services without dealing in cash. Additionally, the research emphasizes that it is imperative for all financial institutions to offer fundamental internet banking capabilities, including online money transmission options and debit cards.

The introduction of green banking guidelines by Bangladesh Bank, local banks have increasingly embraced sustainability reporting. However, challenges such as inconsistent disclosure practices and a lack of standardized frameworks persist. Green Banking Disclosure (GBD) is the term used to describe the disclosure of a bank's environmental initiatives and sustainability performance. This procedure enhances stakeholder trust, promotes accountability, and guarantees transparency. Standardized reporting guidelines are provided by frameworks like the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) and the Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP), which allow stakeholders to evaluate the environmental impact of financial institutions (Cheng, 2014). The strategic importance of GBD is emphasized by empirical evidence. Stakeholder engagement and consumer loyalty are generally more favorable for banks that disclose their sustainability practices. Positioning a bank as a leader in sustainable finance, GBD enhances its corporate image. In addition, GBD is a crucial instrument for regulatory compliance, particularly in jurisdictions with rigorous environmental policies (Dienes, 2016).

Financial performance is a critical factor influencing a firm's ability and willingness to engage in green banking disclosure. Theories such as stakeholder theory, legitimacy theory, and resource-based theory provide insights into this relationship. According to stakeholder theory, businesses must address the interests of all stakeholders, including investors, customers, and regulators, to maintain legitimacy and achieve sustainable success (Freeman, 1984).

The relationship between financial performance and GBD can be comprehended through theoretical lenses such as stakeholder theory and legitimacy theory. Stakeholder theory proposes that firms disclose information to satisfy the expectations of a variety of stakeholders, such as investors, customers, and regulators (Freeman, 1984). Banks that are financially successful are more inclined to invest in GBD as a means of meeting stakeholder demands from this perspective.

This perspective is furthered by legitimacy theory, which posits that organizations participate in GBD to preserve their legitimacy in society. In order to maintain their legitimacy, organizations must ensure that their practices are consistent with societal norms and expectations. The financial performance is crucial, as profitable firms have the resources needed to implement and publish green initiatives (Suchman, 1995).

A positive correlation between financial performance and GBD is generally supported by empirical studies. Green initiatives are prioritized by banks that demonstrate superior performance, which they following disclose in order to improve their reputational capital. This is due to the fact that profitability and liquidity are significant predictors of sustainability disclosure (Chih, 2020).

Bangladesh Bank's green banking guidelines have compelled local banks to prioritize GBD, regardless of their financial performance (Masukujjaman, 2014). There are various barriers to implementing green banking practices in emerging economies. The widespread adoption of green initiatives is often hampered by inadequate regulatory frameworks, lack of public awareness, and limited financial resources. The green banking sector in Bangladesh is still in its early stages, despite the sustainable development initiatives of the Bangladesh Bank. (Masukujjaman, 2014).

A substantial body of empirical research has examined the link between financial performance and environmental disclosure. A positive correlation was found between financial performance and environmental disclosure, suggesting that organizations that are profitable are able to engage in sustainability reporting (Al-Tuwaijri, 2004). organizations with strong financial performance are more likely to invest in voluntary disclosures that aim to enhance their stakeholder relationships and reputations, according to comparable results. (Branco, 2006).

Profitability is a critical determinant of GBD, as it is measured through metrics such as Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE). (Mishra, 2010) contended that profitable banks have the financial resources necessary to invest in green initiatives. These investments frequently generate enduring advantages, such as enhanced operational efficiency and improved stakeholder relations. Banks in Bangladesh that have demonstrated greater profitability have demonstrated a greater dedication to GBD, as they are able to afford the initial expenses associated with sustainable practices (Sharifi, 2015).

Chapter 03: Methodology & Data Collection

3.1 Methodology: A research methodology is a systematic approach for researchers to conduct their studies, ensuring valid, reliable data that meets their goals and objectives. It includes information on the data they will collect, where they will obtain it, how they will collect it, and how they will analyze it. Quantitative analysis was used in this study.

3.1.1 Sample Size: The study mainly focused on the banking sector. For this analysis, 5 banks in Bangladesh have been taken as samples. These banks were selected based on their green banking disclosure report.

3.1.2 Time frame: This research is conducted by collecting data for five years, from 2018 to 2022. The collected data is analyzed based on Bangladesh Bank's green banking guidelines (3 phases), which were last updated in 2011, and the bank's financial performance.

3.1.3 Data Collection: This study's data is all collected from secondary sources. Most of the data from FI reports and climate change disclosures from the bank's annual reports from 2018 to 2022. Besides, these data were also collected from the Green Banking Policy of Bangladesh Bank, Research papers, Journals, and Websites.

3.2 Data Analysis & presentation: For the Green Banking Index, the value of information items can range from 0 to 1. When a company discloses information items in its annual report, it receives "1" and, if not, "0." After collecting the required data, the Green Banking Index is represented in graphic techniques and shown in the theoretical framework. Then, to evaluate the quality of the study, different statistical procedures were applied, such as:

Descriptive Analysis: Green Banking Index and Financial performance have been summarized in the descriptive statistics section. It depicts the mean and standard deviation of green banking and the profitability of banks.

Correlation Analysis: The degree of correlation between the dependent variable: green banking index and the independent variable: profitability has been explained based on the output.

Regression Analysis: Simple Linear Regression model has been conducted for determining the level of relationship of the variables.

3.3 Green Banking Index: Bangladesh Bank is playing a significant role in ensuring green banking practice activity in the banking sector. The bank receives a green banking approach in a formal and organized way in accordance with world standards provided by Bangladesh Bank. With a view to developing green banking practices in the country, an indicative Green Banking Policy and Strategy framework has been developed for the banks. As per the circular of Bangladesh Bank, banks are to implement green banking guidelines in three phases. These are:

Phase A	PA1: Policy formulation and governance
	PA2: Incorporation of environmental risk in customer relationship management (CRM)
	PA3: Initiating in-house environment management
	PA4: Introducing Green Finance
	PA5: Creation of Climate Risk Fund
	PA6: Introducing Green Marketing
	PA7: Online Banking
	PA8: Supporting employee training, consumer awareness and green event
	PA9: Disclosure and reporting of green banking activities
Phase B	PB1: Sector specific environmental policies
	PB2: Green strategic planning
	PB3: Setting up green branches
	PB4: Improved in-house environment management
	PB5: Formulation of bank specific environmental risk management plan and guidelines
	PB6: Difficult programs to educate clients
	PB7: Disclosure and reporting of green banking activities
Phase C	PC1: Designing and introducing innovative products
	PC2: Reporting in standard format with external verification

Table 01: Bangladesh Bank Policy Guidelines for Green Banking

For find out the green banking index of each bank we checked the green banking guideline policy for each year in the green banking disclosure section of the bank's annual report. We checked whether the guideline policy mentioned by Bangladesh Bank was followed or not by looking at the bank's annual report. After checking them, we found the results. (The checking process is given in the Appendix.)

These graphs show us the result of Green Banking Index of 5 banks, which are BRAC, EBL, PRIME, DBBL, and JAMUNA, over the 5 years (2018-2022).

Figure 01: Brac Bank Green Banking Index

Brac Bank: The graph of Brac Bank shows us that, without 2018, Brac Bank followed all the phases of the green banking policy over the years. In 2018, they had 0.89 out of 1. They missed PA5, which is the creation of a climate risk fund, and PA6, Green Marketing, which may be due to insufficient regulatory incentives. However, after 2018, they successfully completed all the phases, which reflects their well-structured approach to environmental risk integration, protective policies, and governance, as well as the strong internal management systems with green banking principles.

Figure 02: EBL Green Banking Index

Eastern Bank PLC (EBL): In the EBL graph, improvements over the years can be visibly noticeable. They started at .83 in 2018 and reached .94 by 2022. However, till now, EBL has not adopted PA5 (Creation of climate risk); they may have prioritized short-term financial goals over long-term sustainability. Besides these other years, they also missed PB1(sector-specific environmental policies), PB3(Setting up green branches), and PC2 (reporting in standard format with external verifications). This may happen because of the complexity of the implementation, high cost, and lack of standardized frameworks. However, they are showed gradual improvement their overall performance.

Figure 03: Prime Bank Green Banking Index

Prime Bank: Among all five banks, the Prime Bank showed the most fluctuations in green banking practices. In 2018,2019, they kept the consistency, but their compliance significantly dropped in 2020 from 0.83 to 0.61, but they recovered gradually in 2021 and 2022. Throughout this time, they were facing difficulty implementing PA5 (Creation of Climate Risk Fund) and PA6 (Green Marketing), most likely either because of limited resources or because of other strategic priorities fighting for their attention. They failed to implement PA2 (Environmental Risk in CRM) in 2020, and also PA8 (Supporting employee training, consumer awareness, and green events) missed some training for employees or the upgrade of the CRM system. Besides this, PB3(Setting up green branches) and PC2 (Reporting in standard format with external verifications) have also been missing for some of the years. However, they are trying to improve their green banking practice over the years.

Figure 04: DBBL Green Banking Index

Dutch Bangla Bank Limited (DBBL): The DBBL graph shows the best performance and well-integrated green strategy by maintaining all the guideline phases from 2018-2022. Undoubtedly, their efforts set a benchmark for other banks. This bank focuses on the benefits of early investments in employee training, internal environmental management, and innovative products in green finance. By completing all the phases from PA1 to PC2, they represent a strong alignment with sustainability goals.

Figure 05: Jamuna Bank Green Banking Index

Jamuna Bank: Jamuna Bank has shown constant improvement in green banking practices over the years. From 2018 to 2022, they increased their green banking practices from 0.78 to 0.94. They are gradually trying to enhance their green banking practices. However, they consistently failed to adopt PA5 (Creation of Climate Risk Fund), which may be due to insufficient regulatory incentives or prioritized short-term financial goals. Also, for some of the years, they missed PB1 (sector-specific environmental policies), PB6 (Difficult programs to educate clients), and PC2 (Reporting in standard format with external verifications). But over time, they tried to boost their overall performance.

Chapter 04: Analysis & Findings

4.1 Analysis: Five years of data (from 2018 to 2022) of five banks are used as samples for the analysis. So, a total of 25 observations has been used in this study. Through the tables, analyzed data observations have been shown. The interpretation of data analysis has also been included in an easy-to-understand way.

4.1.1 Descriptive Statistics: In this descriptive statistics table, includes 5 years of data of 5 banks that's why there are 25 observations in total and 6 parameters such as return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), earnings per share (EPS), the Green Banking Index, and LNTA (log of total assets).

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
ROA	25	0.0054	0.0187	0.011176	0.0030562
ROE	25	0.0593	0.197	0.13328	0.0383097
EPS	25	1.47	12.85	4.7212	2.78275
GREEN BANKING INDEX	25	.61	1.00	.9036	.09840
LNTA	25	12.32	13.29	12.7881	.26326
Valid N (listwise)	25				

The descriptive statistics on dependent variable: Green Bank Index independent variables: ROA, ROE, EPS, LNTA. ROA includes five years of data of 5 banks and their mean score is 0.01117. The maximum mean is 0.0187 and the minimum mean is 0.0054. The standard deviation is 0.0030562. On the other hand, ROE has a mean score of 0.13328. The maximum mean is 0.197 and the minimum mean is 0.0593. The standard deviation is 0.0383097. ROA and ROE, shows

that the banks in the sample performed consistently across the entire sample. For EPS, the mean score is 4.7212. The maximum mean is 12.85 and the minimum mean is 1.47. The standard deviation is 2.78275. EPS has a larger dispersion, indicating that there is a big difference in profitability between banks. Green Bank Index includes five years of data of 5 banks and their mean score is 0.9036. The standard deviation is 0.09840. This Green Banking Index revealed that most of companies are following the same kinds of green initiatives and have low variations. Mean score of LNTA of 5 banks over 5 years is 12.7881. The maximum mean is 13.29 and the minimum mean is 12.32. The standard deviation is 0.26326. Bank with larger assets (LNTA) are in general better off financially, and EPS is positively related to profitability metrics such as ROA and ROE. But with little variation in professional profitability across banks, the data indicates stable financial trends.

4.1.2 Correlation Analysis: The degree of linear strength between two or more variables is measured using correlation analysis. The sample correlation coefficient (r) determines it. The correlation analysis measures how closely two variables move together. A positive correlation means that as one variable increases, the other also increases. A negative correlation means that when one goes up, the other goes down. The strength of this relationship is measured using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r), which ranges from -1 to +1. A high correlation coefficient between two variables identifies collinearity.

Correlations						
		GREEN BANKING INDEX	ROA	ROE	EPS	LNTA
GREEN BANKING INDEX	Pearson Correlation	1	.510**	.440*	.584**	.528**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.009	0.028	0.002	0.007
	N	25	25	25	25	25
ROA	Pearson Correlation	.510**	1	.818**	.441*	0.16
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.009		<.001	0.027	0.445
	N	25	25	25	25	25

ROE	Pearson Correlation	.440*	.818**	1	.737**	0.131
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.028	<.001		<.001	0.533
	N	25	25	25	25	25
EPS	Pearson Correlation	.584**	.441*	.737**	1	0.394
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.002	0.027	<.001		0.051
	N	25	25	25	25	25
LNTA	Pearson Correlation	.528**	0.16	0.131	0.394	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.007	0.445	0.533	0.051	
	N	25	25	25	25	25
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).						

From correlation analysis of the table, we found that GBI has a significant positive correlation with ROA (0.510, $P = 0.009$). This indicates that an increase in green banking practices is positively associated with return on assets, and this relationship is statistically significant at the 0.01 level. Also, there is a significant positive relationship between Green Banking Index and Return on Equity (0.440, $P = 0.028$) at the 0.05 level. Besides ROA, EPS has also (0.584, $P = 0.002$) a strong significant positive relationship with green banking index at the 0.01 level. The relationship between green banking and LNTA (log of total assets) is significant (0.528, $P = 0.007$) at the 0.01 level, which indicating that banks with larger assets tend to have higher green banking involvement. The strongest relationships were found between EPS and GBI (0.584) and ROA and GBI (0.510). This means that banks with higher profitability tend to invest more in green banking. However, ROE and LNTA had weaker correlations, that means a bank's equity returns and size do not strongly influence green banking efforts.

4.1.3 Regression Analysis: With the help of regression analysis, researchers also obtain a measure of the degree of association between two variables. This helps to understand how much each financial indicator (ROA, ROE, EPS, LNTA) affects the Green Banking Index (GBI). The coefficient values tell how much GBI will change if a financial factor increases by one unit.

The regression models for this study have been developed as follows:

$$GBI = \alpha + \beta_1(ROA) + \beta_2(ROE) + \beta_3(EPS) + \beta_4(LNTA) + \varepsilon$$

Variable definition given below,

GBI = Green Banking Index

ROA = Return on Asset

ROE = Return on Equity

EPS = Earnings Per Share

LNTA= Log of Total Assets

α = Constant

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ = Regression coefficients

ε = Error term.

Regression analysis was conducted to understand how the Green Banking Index is affected by four financial predictors: LNTA (Log of Total Assets), ROE (Return on Equity), EPS (Earnings Per Share), and ROA (Return on Assets). The purpose of the analysis was to determine whether these financial indicators significantly affect the Green Banking Index. To achieve this, a regression model was used to test the relationship between the dependent and independent variables.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.767 ^a	.588	.505	.06920

a. Predictors: (Constant), LNTA, ROE, EPS, ROA

The regression analysis, the results demonstrated that the model correlation coefficient (R) is 0.767, which means there is a strong positive connection between the Green Banking Index and

the predictors (LNTA, ROE, EPS, and ROA). This explains that the independent variables are relatively well correlated with dependent variables. According to the value of R square predictors account for 58.8% of the variance in the Green Banking Index. This suggests that the model has a moderate to strong explanatory power. In addition, the adjusted R Square value is 0.505. When more variables are added, this value offers a more accurate measure of model fit and accounts for the number of predictors in the model. A value of 0.505 indicates that the independent variables are still responsible for about 50.5% of the variation in the Green Banking Index after controlling for the number of predictors. And the estimate's standard error is 0.06920.

ANOVA^a

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.137	4	.034	7.133	<.001 ^b
	Residual	.096	20	.005		
	Total	.232	24			

a. Dependent Variable: GREEN BANKING INDEX

b. Predictors: (Constant), LNTA, ROE, EPS, ROA

The ANOVA results show that the overall model is significant ($p < 0.001$) and the predictors explain a significant portion of the variation in the Green Banking Index. This means that financial factors do play an important role in predicting green banking performance.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.295	.830		-.355	.726
	ROA	.241	.095	.747	2.538	.020
	ROE	-.018	.010	-.707	-1.750	.096
	EPS	.024	.010	.687	2.466	.023
	LNTA	.083	.065	.221	1.271	.218

a. Dependent Variable: GREEN BANKING INDEX

The coefficient table explained the contribution of each predictor to the Green Banking Index (GBI). Here, the Green Banking Index as the dependent variable and ROA (Return on Assets), ROE (Return on Equity), EPS (Earnings per Share), and LNTA (Natural Log of Total Assets) as predictors. Here, coefficient of -0.295, represents the predicted value of the Green Banking Index when all predictors are zero. However, the constant is not statistically significant, as its p-value is 0.726, which is greater than the threshold of 0.05. Among the predictors, ROA has a positive and statistically significant relationship with the Green Banking Index (GBI), as indicated by its coefficient of 0.241 and a p-value of 0.020. This explains that for every unit increase in ROA, the GBI increases by 0.241. Similarly, EPS also shows a positive and statistically significant effect on the GBI, with a coefficient of 0.024 and a p-value of 0.023. This means that an increase in EPS is associated with an increase in the GBI. But on the other hand, ROE has a negative coefficient of -0.018, indicating a slight negative relationship with the Green Banking Index. However, this relationship is not statistically significant, as its p-value is 0.096, which is above 0.05. Also, LNTA, which represents the log of total assets, has a positive coefficient of 0.083, which show a positive relationship with the Green Banking Index. But, with a p-value of 0.218, this relationship is not statistically significant.

4.2 Findings: The analysis explained that financial performance plays an important role in showing how well banks can adopt green banking practices. Banks with higher Return on Assets

(ROA) and Earnings Per Share (EPS) are more likely to invest in sustainability efforts. This indicates that when banks earn more profits, they may have more resources to support green initiatives, such as financing eco-friendly projects, adopting digital banking, and improving energy efficiency.

The Green Banking Index (GBI) exhibits significantly high variance in the analysis, with a moderately high R-squared value. The model included financial indicators such as ROA, ROE, EPS, and LNTA as predictors for GBI. First of all, the correlation analysis showed a strong positive relationship between the Green Banking Index (GBI) and ROA (0.510), indicating that banks with higher returns on assets are more likely to implement robust green banking practices. GBI also positively correlated with EPS (0.584), indicating that profitability per share encourages green banking practices more. Banks that earn higher profits from their assets and earnings per share tend to engage more in green banking. The regression analysis further confirmed that with the p-values of 0.020 and 0.023, ROA and EPS significantly impact green banking adoption. However, the findings also found that Return on Equity (ROE) and bank size (LNTA) did not strongly influence green banking. Although larger banks generally have more resources, their size alone does not determine their commitment to sustainability. The p-values for ROE (0.096) and LNTA (0.218) show that these factors do not significantly affect a bank's decision to implement green banking practices. That means profitability matters more than size when investing in sustainability. Additionally, the ANOVA test confirmed that the overall model used in the study was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Financial factors play an important role in predicting green banking performance. These kinds of findings were previously performed in developed countries; such as: European banks (Weber, 2017) and U.S. banks (Furrer, 2012) found that green banking improves financial stability and enhances a bank's reputation. Similar studies in the UK (Clarkson, 2011) and Canada (Sharma, 2005) found that banks with strong environmental policies performed better in the stock market and gained more customer trust. Moreover, the findings from this study show that financially stable banks practice green banking more efficiently.

Chapter 05: Recommendation & Conclusion

5.1 Recommendation:

- ❖ Banks with higher Return on Assets (ROA) and Earnings Per Share (EPS) invest more in sustainability and to gain more profitability, banks should focus on cost efficiency, investment in digital banking, and offering green financial products.
- ❖ Encouraging businesses and individuals to adopt eco-friendly solutions through green loans and sustainable investment products will definitely help strengthen green banking initiatives.
- ❖ Banks like Eastern Bank (EBL) and Jamuna Bank, did not create a Climate Risk Fund (PA5). To enhance green banking, regulatory authorities should provide some tax benefits to encourage banks to allocate resources for managing climate risks.
- ❖ Some banks also did not fully implement sector-specific environmental policies (PB1). For that banks need to create tailored strategies that align with Bangladesh Bank's green banking guidelines to ensure compliance and effectiveness.
- ❖ Training employees and educating customers about green banking practices are crucial. Banks should organize offline or online workshops and implement awareness programs to enhance sustainability knowledge.
- ❖ Banks like Jamuna, Prime, Eastern still now struggled with standardized reporting (PC2). But by adopting global frameworks like the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) or Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP) will improve transparency and consistency in sustainability disclosures.
- ❖ Regulators should offer some policy incentives such as: reduce capital requirements for green investments, and provide credit support to banks that focus on eco-friendly banking.
- ❖ Banks should take green banking as a long-term investment, not only just a regulatory requirement. Aligning green initiatives with financial strategies will lead to greater stability, profitability, and customer trust.

By applying these recommendations, banks can improve green banking adoption, also enhance financial performance, and contribute to environmental sustainability.

5.2 Conclusion:

This study shows that a green banking index helps banks to become more sustainable and profitable. There is a positive relationship found between green banking and financial performance of banks. Which means banks that earn more profits (ROA and EPS) are more efficiently invest in green initiatives. Banks like Dutch Bangla Bank Limited (DBBL) and Brac have done a great job they following green banking guidelines properly. While others, like Prime Bank and Jamuna Bank, still have areas to improve. And to improve those areas, banks should invest in digital banking, provide green loans, train employees, and follow global reporting standards. However, just being a large bank does not guarantee strong green banking practices. That's why regulators should also give incentives to encourage more green banking efforts.

Green banking plays a crucial role in making impactful investments toward establishing green buildings and eco-friendly industries. The world continuously facing different environmental, social, and economic challenges that threaten sustainable living. And these issues require an urgent and collective effort from both developed and developing nations, especially countries like Bangladesh. So, to improve these crucial issues or conditions whether it is environmental, social, or economic every financial institution and organization must commit to green banking and do sustainable finance, whether it is more profitable or not, it should not be the prime concern. Different countries already experience the impacts of green banking and its relationship with profitability. Although developed nations have stronger policies and resources to support green initiatives. And now, developing countries like Bangladesh also started prioritize green banking to ensure long-term financial stability and environmental sustainability.

This research also provides valuable insights for both banks and governments in promoting green banking and ensuring financial and environmental sustainability. For banks, adopting green banking practices helps in enhanced profitability, reduced operational costs, and improved customer trust. It also helps them to expand green financial products, attract eco-conscious investors, and comply with regulatory requirements, avoiding potential penalties. Green banking also reduces financial and environmental risks by shifting investments toward sustainable industries and eco-friendly projects. To finance eco-friendly projects, banks must check companies' backgrounds to determine whether their projects harm the environment. For example, rather than approve a loan for a plastic company, a bank can give that loan to a company that is

adapting greenery or trying to keep the environment friendly. On the other hand, policymakers can use this research to enhance green banking regulations, introduce financial incentives, and ensure stricter compliance monitoring. By aligning policies with global sustainability frameworks such as the Equator Principles (Equator, 2020) and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), they can integrate Bangladesh's banking sector into international green finance initiatives.

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Appendix

Appendix 01: Green Banking Index checking process.

	BRAC				EBL				PRIME				DBBL				JAMUNA				
	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	
PHASEA	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PA1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PA2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PA3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PA4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PA5	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
PA6	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PA7	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PA8	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PA9	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
PHASEB																					
PB1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
PB2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PB3	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PB4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PB5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PB6	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1
PB7	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PHASEC																					
PC1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
PC2	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
TOTAL=	16	18	18	18	18	15	16	16	17	17	15	15	11	14	15	18	14	15	16	16	17
GBI	0.89	1	1	1	1	0.83	0.89	0.89	0.94	0.94	0.83	0.61	0.78	0.83	0.83	0.78	0.83	0.83	0.89	0.89	0.94

Appendix 02: Five Banks Financial Performance Data

Bank Name	Year	Total Asse	ROA	ROE	EPS	GREEN BANKING INDEX
BRAC	2018	315,417	1.87%	19.25%	4.5	0.89
	2019	369,404	1.64%	15.60%	4.26	1
	2020	396,982	1.19%	10.69%	3.26	1
	2021	449,084	1.31%	11.00%	3.71	1
	2022	563,239	1.14%	10.22%	3.85	1
EBL	2018	282,451	1.15%	13.83%	4.17	0.83
	2019	335,163	1.30%	16.52%	4.94	0.89
	2020	336,936	1.22%	15.04%	5.05	0.89
	2021	388,815	1.28%	15.51%	4.88	0.94
	2022	455,989	1.21%	15.46%	4.76	0.94
PRIME	2018	295,613	0.76%	8.31%	1.94	0.83
	2019	323,788	0.54%	5.93%	1.47	0.83
	2020	347,502	0.54%	6.31%	1.59	0.61
	2021	389,878	0.84%	10.61%	2.75	0.78
	2022	433,410	0.98%	12.93%	3.55	0.83
DBBL	2018	346,468	1.30%	19.70%	10.13	1
	2019	390,362	1.20%	17.20%	12.85	1
	2020	427,355	1.30%	18.40%	8.69	1
	2021	593,883	1.10%	16.10%	7.99	1
	2022	555,478	1.20%	14.40%	8.14	1
JAMUNA	2018	225,018	1.10%	13.89%	3.09	0.78
	2019	242,928	1.11%	14.80%	3.48	0.83
	2020	241,533	1.10%	12.93%	3.56	0.83
	2021	264,321	0.98%	10.88%	3.31	0.89
	2022	282,636	0.58%	7.69%	2.11	0.94